

Impact of Social Media Usage on Organisational Image Mediated by Customer Trust

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of social media usage (information search, marketing & branding and customer relations) on organizational image mediated by customer trust. A sample size of 243 respondents were selected using convenient sampling technique among those who are actively purchasing online platforms in Malaysia. The questionnaire with a 5 point Likert-Scale was used to collect the data. The data was analysed using structural equation modelling via AMOSE software. The result shows that social media usage has no significant impact on organizational image. Also social media usage has no significant impact on customer trust except information search of social media usage. However this study found that level of trust has a positive and significant impact on organizational image suggesting that when level of trust increases, the perceived organizational image also enhanced among the customers. Therefore managers and decision makers must ensure customer's level of trust is build and developed and maintained to improve organizational image. This research could improve further with the use of qualitative research approach by conducting interview or an observation, or can conduct an experimental research design where groups of respondents may be put under observation with different context. This could be more accurate than just expressing or rating a scale questionnaire. This will also enable researchers to avoid any baseness in completing a survey questionnaire. Also this research will enhance its result if focus on one particular industry where by identifying social media users regularly to respond the items included in the questionnaire. Also revising the social media usage items could further improve by using technology acceptance model variables.

Keywords: Social media, Organizational Image, Trust, Malaysia

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Research Background

The aim of this study is to examine the impact of social media on organisational image mediated by trust. The corporate image has been recognized in achieving business goal posts and stay competitive via the social media platform (Bilgin, 2018; Nisar et al, 2019). Consumers who like or dislike the products or services can express their opinions through forums or blogs, product review websites, emails and social networking sites (Erkan& Evans, 2018). Social media can be viral and uncontrollable. Social networking has created significant challenges for the company's public relations and has built a trusting relationship with the followers or readers and they have influencing power over the public opinion (Dabula, 2017). A case study reported that 258 respondents, among the age between 18 and 41 years old found that 2.44 percent never; 26.83 percent sometimes; 51.22 percent often; and 19.51percent always, on the frequency of the social media users actively participating discussions in online social networks (DelceaPaun, &Bradea, 2015). Another study showed that there were million internet users, and most of them were using Facebook as social media platform (Hashim, Nor, &Janor, 2017). Also it was reported that most of the entrepreneurs believed that social media is the future way of doing their social commerce (social media business) (Hashim et al, 2017). In fact, most of the business owners believed that they need to adopt and engage in with social media platforms such as Twitter, Facebook and LinkedIn to introduce, promote and communicate their partners and customers (Hashim et al, 2017). The past statistics showed that in year 2018, the number of social network users in worldwide was 2.62 billion and it's

increasingly every year (Dimitrova&Matthes, 2018). The social media adoption among the Malaysian was 19.05 million in year 2018 and it's increasing over the coming years (Zabha et al, 2019). In the most recent report indicated that 84.2 percent uses Facebook, 6.09 percent uses Pinterest, 3.82 percent uses Twitter, 2.83 percent uses Youtube, 2.24 percent uses Instagram, and 0.42 percent uses Tumblr (Statecounter, 2020).

In Malaysia, organization spent millions of USD every year on marketing activities via social media (Musa et al, 2016). It was argued that by having a profile in social media will not itself increase awareness or enable an influx of user participation in the social media site (Adetunji, 2018). It was reported that even those organizations that claims that they use Web 2.0 applications and tools, they are not clearly understand the meaning of adoption of social media (Ahmad et al, 2018). This creates tension among the managers to identify the key determinants of successful usage of social media platform (Salo, 2017). In addition to this, social media have changed the way marketing activities have performed in terms of advertising and promotion (Seo& Park, 2018). Social media not only influence organizations marketing activities, but also has influence individual consumer behavior from information acquisition to post-purchase behavior through expression of dissatisfaction statements or behaviors in social media platforms (Palalic et al, 2020). This emergence of differences in behavior urged researchers to treat social media as distinct research area (Hu et al, 2015; Laroche et al., 2012; Kapoor et al, 2018). However, studies on both social media and organization image through trust are quite new and few (Akar&Topcu, 2011; Kapoor et al, 2018).

1.2. Problem Statement

Despite the growing stream of studies on social media; however, to date the study of the impact of social media adoption or usage by organization through level of trust is still limited and few (Seo& Park, 2018). The past studies that were carried out on social media can be categories into individual, organizational, social, security or privacy and others (Tajudeen, 2014). In her study, she have reviewed hundreds of research papers that were done on social media and revealed that 201 studies were carried out in addressing various issues from organizational perspective covering range of organizational related issues such as usage (Individual), usage (organization), social issues and security & privacy. Also number of studies on social media, especially in Malaysian context is limited and less emphasis was made to investigate the effect of social media in relations with organizational image and mediating effect of trust. Furthermore, the studies that were carried out on social media in relations with organizational issues are also very less or limited to marketing, branding & word-of-mouth, general organizational usage, spending & impact, public relations & customer relations and recruitment (Tajudeen, 2014).

This indicates that research on social media has not grown rapidly (Leung et al, 2017; Leonardi, &Vaast, 2017; Li et al, 2017). Although there were many academic research on social media, most of the social media related articles comprises of newspaper and magazine articles and blogs were emphasised on examining the impact of social media on branding, customer relations and marketing (Fletcher & Park, 2017; Akar&Topcu, 2011). As mentioned, even though previous studies that examined the determinants of social media usage, most of the studies investigated the social media usage from individual perspective (Cao & Yu, 2019; Tajudeen et al, 2018). This shows that past studies focused on social media usage and its subsequent impact on the organizations' performance were relatively few. Despite the fact that the social media has been identified as a significant factor in enhancing social connections, the depth and significance of social connections and relationships for building trust has not been sufficiently explored (Arora et al, 2019; Ellison, et al., 2007; Joinson, 2008, April). Also there were only handful of studies done on examining the impact of social media on organisational image (Kissel, &Büttgen, 2015; Warner-Søderholm et al, 2018). There were also very few studies that have attempted in examining the impact of social media on customer trust (Zhang & Li, 2019; Warner-Søderholm et al, 2018).

The past literature suggested that there were very few or less emphasis is being made in examining the effect of social media usage effect on organizational image through trust. Therefore, this research would contribute to investigate this with the aim to fill up such gaps, by combining different theories and frameworks and by using survey methods an integrated model was developed to study the impact of social media usage on organizational image through trust of customers. Therefore the objective of this study is to examine the effect of Social media usage on organizational image, effect of social media usage on customer trust and examine the mediating effect of customer trust on the relationship between social media usage and organizational image.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.2. Review of key Concepts

2.2.1. Social Media

Social media was defined in a several of ways. Some of the social media definitions such as Boyde and Ellison (2008)'s were more acceptable among the scholars than others. For example Boyde and Ellison (2008)'s definition received more than 13,000 citations in google scholar (Wolf, Sims & Yang, 2018), while definitions of social media by Kietzmann et al, (2011)' has received 3,000 citations (Wolf et al, 2018). Similarly definition of social media provided in 2020 by Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) received 11,000 citations on google scholar (Wolf et al, 2018). The recent trend shows that social media related definitions are being revised or created new definition and continue on enhancing old definitions due to the increasing usage, adoption and development in the use of social media (Kapoor et al., 2017). The Table 3 below shows various definitions of Social media from 2007 until 2017.

Table 1: Definitions of Social Media

Author(s)	Definitions
Boyd and Ellison (2007, p.221)	Social Media has been defined as web-based services which enables individuals to create profiles, generate user lists whom they have connection visibility of relationships between users
Diga and Kelleher (2009)	Referred Social Media as "social media sites"
Kietzmann et al (2011, p.243)	Social media is defined as web-based applications which enables individuals to identify their profiles, engage in conversation, sharing information, profiles accessibility to realise the presence of others, building relationships and form groups
Huang and Benyoucef, (2013 p. 246).	Social media is referred as an 'internet-based applications built on Web 2.0, while Web 2.0 refers to a concept as well as a platform for harnessing collective intelligence'
Steenkamp and Hyde-Clarke (2014, p.92)	The term Social Media is used to 'describe online tools and utilities that allow communication of information, participation and collaboration'
Ouiridi et al. (2014)	Defined social media as web-based online and mobile platforms that enables users to exchange information or idea and add geographical information to user-generated content
Kapoor et al (2017)	Social media is defined as a set of information exchange or sharing through technologies such as Web 2.0 that facilitate interactions and networking
Kazemian and Grant (2020)	Define the term "Social Media" as web-based tool that facilitated online transaction between individuals and communities through effective communications in terms of exchanging information '

Based on the definitions given on the above Table 1, social media is a web-based platform to create profiles and connect with people to build relationship (Boyde& Ellison, 2007). The definition of social media took a turn when social media was referred as a 'social media sites' (Diga& Kelleher, 2009). Kietzmann et al (2011) added few more attributes to definition of social media such as conversation, sharing information, realize the presence of others and form groups. In 2013, social media is referred as an 'internet based applications build on Web-2.0'. The use of Web 2.0 in defining social media resulted the use of the term online more often in social media definitions. For example in 2014, social media is as web-based online and mobile platform to share information, participate, collaborate and generated geographical information to user generated contents (Steenkamp & Hyde-Clarke, 2014; Ouiridi et al, 2014). In 2017, the definition of social media started using the world interaction and networking. As result Kapoor et al (2017) defined social media as exchange of information through Web2.0 technologies which facilitates interaction and networking. More recently social media is defined as web-based communication tool that enabled interaction between two or more individuals and communicates to share information on online platforms (Kazemian& Grant, 2020).

The definitions in the past have clearly indicated three main elements of social media (1) web-based online plate form, (2) communication and profile creation and (3) networking and information sharing. Therefore 'social media'

can be defined as a web-based online or mobile platform that enables individuals or organisations to communicate, exchange information, build profile and enable interaction and networking.

2.2.2. Organisational Image

Organisational image is an overall impression of the customer’s mind or memory because of the accumulation of the interaction of feelings, ideas, and attitudes and after sales services or experiences with the organization (Putro, 2016). This accumulative of their feelings and experience will transform into positive or negative impact on the organisation (Ou&Verhoef, 2017). This will be retrieved and recalled when organisation name is heard or brought to the mind of the customer (Chakraborty & Bhat, 2018). Organisational images refer to stakeholders or corporate audiences’ impressions, knowledge or beliefs on an organisation (Lievens, 2017). An organisation may have multiple images in different perspective of stakeholders or corporate audiences (Harvey et al, 2017). For instance, the investors and executives holding the organisation image as economic performer (“*company financial image*”) because they rely on the economic figures as a basis for investment (Lievens, 2017). In general, the society is holding the organisation image as social performer (also known as ‘corporate social performance’) (Lievens, 2017). While the customers will see the organisation as a products and services provider (“*product image or service image*”) and lastly, as an employer or employment image for the current employees and applicants (Lievens, 2017).

Table 2: Definitions of Organisational Image

Author(s)	Definition
Moffitt (1994, p.166)	An organizational image is the ‘ <i>shared meanings, attitudes, knowledge, and opinions</i> ’ of organizational stakeholders,
Hatch and Schultz (1997, p.359)	Organisational image is a ‘ <i>holistic and vivid impression held by an individual or a particular group towards an organization and is a result of sense-making by the group and communication by the organization of a fabricated and projected picture of itself</i> ’
Massey(2003, April)	An organizational image is the product of discourse between organizations and stakeholders, not simply the result of one-way communication that ipso facto produces a desired image in the minds of the target audience
Parent and Foreman (2007)	Organisational image was defined as members’ beliefs about how outsiders see their organization.
Frandsen (2017)	Organizational image is referred as a cognitive construct which is perceived by general public of the organisation as an impression created in the mind of customers
Lievens,(2017)	Organizational image is defined as impression of people towards organisation globally in terms of their loose structures of knowledge and belief about organisation ‘

In 1994 organisational image was defined as opinions of organisational stakeholders towards the organisation through accumulated knowledge, attitude and shared meanings (Moffitt, 1994). Later organisational image was defined as holistic and vivid impression of a particular group of people towards organisation and how they picture the organisation (Hatch & Schultz, 1997). Also organisational image was defined as the overall impression of the public on the company (Nguyen & Leblanc, 2001).They had identified the determinants of organizational image in the service industry from the customers’ point of view (Nguyen & Leblanc, 2001). There were five factors influencing customer point of view of corporate image in services companies that are reputation, corporate identity, services offered, physical environment, and contact personnel. As a result, it shows that organisational image was derived mainly from reputation (Nguyen & Leblanc, 2001). Similarly, Massey (2003, April) defined organisational image was the image in the mind of customers or target audience due to the two way communication between target audience and organisational members.In 2007, again organisational image was defined from the external perspectives where it was seen as image perceived by external stakeholders about the organisation. 10 years later also the key aspect of organisational image was maintained in the definition as it focus on global impression, knowledge and belief about organisation (Frandsen, 2017; Lievens, 2017). However based on the definition in the Table 2, definitions of organizational image is divided into external perspectives such as customer and external stakeholder point of view while the other aspects is based on internal stakeholders such as employee and management perspective of organizational image. Therefore organizational

image is the impression of customers and external stakeholders of an organisation and the perception of organisation in the mind of customers.

2.2.3. Customer Trust

Trust is a belief or expectation about others’ good intention during a social interaction (Chang, Liu & Shen, 2017) or can be defined as a psychological state which is comprised of the intention to accept the risk based on positive expectations of the intentions or behaviours of another person (Rousseau, et al., 1998). Similarly, trust has been defined as the belief that the trustee will behave according to our expectation (Reiersen, 2017). Trust can be measured as probability which is quite subjective (Ruan et al, 2017). Some definitions of trust emphasises expectations, predictability, and confidence in others’ behaviour (PytlíkZillig, & Kimbrough, 2016). But in this research, trust is referred as customer trust. The definitions below shows some of the conceptual definition of customer trust.

Table 3: Definitions of Customer Trust

Author(s)	Definition
Deutschi, (1958).	Customer trust is the confidence and belief which customer attach with the organization or brand expects what he or she consider should be delivered
Rotter (1967)	Customer trust is defined as the level of reliability ensured by the organization to customer within a given exchange relationship
Costabile, et al (2000)	Customer trust is defined as the reliability of the customer's perspective based on past experience based on the sequences of transactions or interactions leading to fulfillment of expectations of product performance and satisfaction
McKnight and Chervany (2002)	Customer trust is defined as the belief allows customers to willingly become vulnerable to mobile Internet site after having taken the Internet site’s characteristics into consideration.
Thomas (2009: 346)	Customer trust is defined as customer expectancy of positive outcomes, outcomes that one can receive based on the expected action of service provider
Salciuviene et al. (2011)	Customer trust is defined as a ground for constructiveness, credibility and confidence in sales representative’s reliability and competence

In the past, the concept of customer trust has attracted much attention among organizational theory researchers and marketing practitioners (Alalwan et al, 2018). Since long ago customer trust was defined as confidence and belief that customer attached with company or their brands (Deutschi, 1959), or level of reliability ensured by organization to deliver what they had promised (Rotter, 1967). Similarly after 30 years, definition of customer trust remained same although definition extended in covering the aspects such as experienced in the past in interaction with organisation and whether such experience is positive in meeting customer expectation (Costabile et al, 2000). In 2002, with the emergence of mobile technology and mobile commerce, the definition of customer trust took a new turn ad defined as belief of customer that allows them to willingly become vulnerable to mobile sites run on online platforms after customer consider characteristics of online platforms (McKnight &Chervany, 2002). The essential aspects of customer trust remain same as Thomas (2009) considered elements such as customer expectancy of positive outcomes received from their encounter with the organisation. More recently customer satisfaction was defined as ground of constructiveness, credibility, and confidence in sales force competences, and reliability as well as product (Saciuviene et al, 2011). In a marketing context, trust is usually linked to customer expectations concerning the organization’s capability to keep its promises (Zhang & Li, 2019).The role of customer trust in forming behavioural intentions to engage with future transactions is well defined in the past literature (Busalim et al, 2019). For example, customer trust enables an organisation to maintain customer loyalty (Elizar et al, 2020.). Therefore customer trust is defined as belief and perception of customer towards organisation’s fulfillment of promises made in delivery of services and products.

2.3. Review Past Literature

Many studies applied social behaviour theories and models to develop conceptual framework to study the effect of social media influence on organizational image or how level of trust have been influenced by social media (Ngai, et al., 2015). For the last two to three decades, many researches were conducted to understand, explain and predict the key determinants of social media adoption at individual and organisational level (Abbasi et al, 2018). Most of the behavioural theories begins to focus on relationship between social media adoption and its effects on organisational outcomes (Qi, & Chau, 2018). Due to this, large number of theories related to technology adoption have been introduced and tested to examine the determinants of adoption decisions and organisational outcomes (Lai, 2017). Some of the theories that have been frequently used or cited in the past literature include Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 2011), Theory of Reasoned Action (Ajzen&Fishbein, 2004), Technology Acceptance Model extended (Venkatesh& Davis, 2000), Innovation Diffusion Theory (Rogers, 2002), and Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 2003).

Since the focus of this present research is on three key concepts such as social media, organisational image and trust, this research try to review the research on these areas. For example many research in the past have attempted to measure organisational image using corporate or organisational reputation (Etter, Ravasi, & Colleoni, 2019), corporate image (Agbo&Asadu, 2016), brand image (Jayasuriya, Azam, &Ferdous, 2017). There were many studies, which shows that social media marketing enhances and have positive significant impact on organisational image in terms of brand and corporate reputation (Becker & Lee, 2019; Cheung, Pires, & Rosenberger 2019; Jokinen, 2016). The research on social media linking with organisational image has increased by many fold in examining the effect of social media usage on organisational or brand image (Kalejahi, Ramezani, &Rostamzadeh, 2019; Stojanovic, Andreu &Curras-Perez, 2018; Lian&Yoong, 2018).

Similarly, many researches were carried out and examined the impact of social media on trust (Mainardes& Cardoso, 2019; Lou & Yuan, 2019; Cheng, Fu, & de Vreede, 2017), customer trust (Li, Teng, & Chen, 2020; Zhang & Li, 2019; Choi & Lee, 2017) corporate brand trust (Chen, & Cheng, 2019; Jakic, Wagner, & Meyer, 2017; Ullusu, Erdem, &Durmuş, 2016). These studies found that social media marketing has enhances customer trust towards corporate brand (Chen, & Cheng, 2019; Jakic et al, 2017; Ullusu et al, 2016). It was argued that customers can express their feelings through social media, hence it helps to enhance the trust among the social media users in respect of products, services provided by organisations (Singhal, 2016). In the past, research shows that social media marketing has influence on development of trust through Electronic Word-of-Mouth (EWoM) (Ryu& Park, 2020; Chu & Chen, 2019; Prasad, Gupta, &Ttotala, 2017). In terms of the mediating effect of trust, there were a significant number of researches which contributed to this field of research in examining the influence of social media on organisational image through trust (Singh et al, 2020; Sanny et al, 2020; Bilgin, 2018).

This suggests that social media plays a pivotal role to promote the social connections, although the depth and significance of these connections to the creation of trust has not been well developed. Also there were many researches carried out on examining the impact of social media on organisation image or brand image, very little emphasis is being made to examine the mediating effect of customer trust on brand image. Therefore it is concluded that little research conducted on examining the impact of social media on organisational image mediated by trust. Therefore, this study will focus on examining the effect of social media on organisational image mediated by trust. To address this issue the following conceptual framework is being developed to achieve the investigation.

2.4. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

The social media usage by the organisation and its effectiveness depends on organisational attributes such as age, size and type (Dodokh& Al-Maaitah, 2019). There are three key aspects of social media usage such as social media usage for marketing, customer relations and service (Dodokh& Al-Maaitah, 2019). The social media usage change the way customer express their evaluation, and the increasing dynamism and heterogeneity that characterise social media reputation effect the organisational image (Etter et al, 2019). Social media influences on organisational image was positive and significant in a study which was conducted in examining the influence of social media usage on destination image (Kim et al, 2017). A study conducted to examine the impact of social media usage on organisational image during crisis, found that social media has significant influence on organisational image during crisis (Vistbacka, 2017). Also it was found that during the crisis, one of the most effective strategy is communication through social media to sustain corporate brand image (Singh et al, 2020). A study conducted in Kenya revealed that customer responds positively towards social media advertising and argued that social media advertising could help organizations to build their corporate image (Amegbe, Owino, &Kerubo, 2017). A study conducted in Turkey found that social media marketing usage significantly influences brand image and loyalty (Bilgin, 2018). However they found a weak influence of social media on brand image through brand awareness (Bilhin, 2018). In Malaysia, it was found that social media advertising activities has a positive and significant effect on brand equity dimensions such as brand image, brand loyalty and brand preference of customers (Hanaysha, 2016). Another study conducted in Malaysia during 2018 revealed that automobile brand with notable presence on social media such as YouTube, Facebook, Twitter and Instagram engage heavily on social media promotions , advertising, and word-of-mouth tend corporate brand equity such as organisational image (Adetunji, Rashid&Ishak, 2018). Therefore the following hypothesis was formulated

H1: There is a significant and positive influence of social media usage on organisational image

As social media enables to build customer trust, it was argued that social media enable organisations to promote customer engagement with organisation activities to foster customer trust on organisation's products and services (Singhal, 2016). Another study concluded that e-commerce website through social media (Facebook) has significant and positive impact on customer trust (Hariguna, &Berlilana, 2017). It was also found that such social media related e-commerce websites only effects customer trust through quality of information, quality of system and quality of services (Hariguna, &Berlilana, 2017). An experiment was carried out and found that user-generated content of social media networks has significant influence on customer's cognitive trust (Choi & Lee, 2017). Similarly they found that product reviews in closed social media networking system effects customer's cognitive and emotional trust than open social networking system (Choi & Lee, 2017). A study conducted in 2018, found that social media communities enables to build customer trust towards brand trust (Liu et al, 2018). A study conducted in Cyprus found that customer's social media interaction builds customer trust towards the products (Esenyel&Girgen, 2019). Similar result was reported from a study which was conducted in aviation sector of Turkey, where they found that social media related digital and online marketing campaigns were more effective in enhancing customer trust towards the brands compared to traditional marketing campaigns (Tümer et al, 2019). Strong evidence was reported through statistical data analysis indicating that social media usage (marketing) has significant impact on customer trust through social media website quality (Manzoor et al, 2020). Also the enhancing social media website quality improve customer trust leading to potential purchasing intention (Manzoor et al, 2020). In Addition to this, the personality and information disclosure from social media usage had a positive and significant effect on e-word-of-mouth and e-word-of-mouth has a significant and positive impact on customer trust (Seo, Park & Choi, 2020). Therefore the following hypothesis for formulated

H2: There is a significant and positive influence of social media usage on customer trust

Seo et al (2020) found that customer trust has a positive and significant effect on brand awareness and brand image. Also it was found that customer trust increases, the organisational image in terms of brand image and perception of organisation in the eyes of customer improved (Deheshti, AdabiFirouzjah&Alimohammadi, 2016). Since customer trust depends how customer perceive the level of service quality, product reliability and information available for customers, which forms the impression and image of the organisation (Liat et al, 2017). It was argued that when customer's perceived level of trust increases towards organisational products, brand image and overall service delivery results positive organisational image (Song, Wang & Han, 2019). The customer trust level increase when organisation starts to fulfill the promises made to customer (Agag& El-Masry, 2017). As result reliability and dependability of the organisation improves leading to positive organisational image (Hwang & Choi, 2019). From customer perspectives, when organisation engage in more transparent and reliable delivery process causes customer impression on organisation become more positive leading to positive organisational image (Yilmaz & Ari, 2017). Therefore the following hypothesis is formulated

H3: There is significant and positive influence of customer trust on organisational image

In the past most of the research emphasised on testing the mediating effect of trust from organisational behavioural context rather than from marketing perspectives such as relationship between job satisfaction and workforce spirituality (Hassan et al, 2016), mediating effect of trust on socialisation, information sharing and innovation (Kulangara et al, 2016), the mediating effect of trust on the relationship between high performance and employee outcomes (Min, Zhu & Bambacas, 2020), and mediating role of brand trust on brand loyalty and brand image (Mabkhot, Shaari & Salleh, 2017). Adebisin and Mwalugha (2020) found that customer trust has a significant mediating effect on the relationship between degree of trust and intention to use healthcare product. The mediating effect of customer trust or trust on the causal relationship between organisational image and social media usage or marketing is less emphasised despite that customer trust on brand or organisational image is enhanced through social media usage or adoption. It was strongly believed that customer trust associated with the brand enhances the social media usage to influence organisational image. Therefore the following hypothesis is formulated:

H4: Customer trust mediates the causal impact of social media on organisational image

III. RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHDOLOGY

Explanatory research design has been applied to this research to identify the cause and effect relationship. The explanatory research design is considered as the most suitable method of examination for this research study as it can measure the correlative nature with the emphasis on instrumental relationship between variables, and more importantly it can explain for the descriptive information (Gray, 2013). Moreover, explanatory design helps to assess why and how there is a relationship between two or more variables (Bellemare, Masaki & Pepinsky, 2017). Hence, the impact of social media usage (independent) on organisational image (dependent) mediated by trust (mediating factor) among the customers who are active in social media platforms in Malaysia. The quantitative research methodology technique has been applied to interpret results with a motive to assist the accumulation of information from a relatively wider number of participants (Taylor, Bogdan & DeVault, 2015). As the research aim is to gather information related to social media and its impact on organisational image mediated by level of trust is crucial to undertake research among number of groups that would ultimately help in making comparison. This method would also help in generalizing wider population size and attain numerical information that would further assist in accomplishing statistical analysis which would further facilitate in defining relation among both the variables (Weis & Willems, 2017).

3.2. Data Collection Method

Primary data collection method has been employed to accumulate information as the research aim is to attain the impact of social media usage on organisational image mediated by level of customer trust. As the industry is competitive and perception of participants who are actively engage in social media usage changes from time to time. It is crucial to attain primary data and analyse it in a statistical manner. With the research design being explanatory and quantitative to represent data, collecting using the primary technique would be most suitable in this context. The target population for this research was consumers who are mainly purchasing online platforms, particularly social media platform in Malaysia. , The sample size of this research is 243 and convenience sampling was used to due to the limited time available for collecting and completing the research.

3.3. Research Instrument

In this research, questionnaire has been used to attain participants view on the defined area of study. Survey or questionnaires is an effective method to collect data or information relating of the individual's attitudes, views, behaviours, and feelings (Brace, 2018). To examine the variables to measure social media usage and its impact on organisational image mediated by level of customer trust in Malaysia. Statistical analysis is required to test these variables computable data obtained from the questionnaire or survey. The questionnaire consisted of two Parts, where Part 1 was Demographic Information of respondents, and Part 2 was the research questions which included all variables such as social media usage (information search, marketing and branding and customer relationship), organisational image and level of trust. All the questions were framed in relation to research topic employing a 5-point Likert scale option for respondents to provide their response (Wang & Krosnick, 2020). The scale included 5 options (strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree) to understand respondents exact perception on the precise questions.

3.4. Respondents

243 respondents are grouped into 6 clusters as shown in Table 1, which including gender, ethnic, age group, program, level of study, length of study. In this research, total of 350 questionnaires were distributed to relevant group of consumers purchasing online in Malaysia. The detail of the respondents are given in the below table

Table 4: Demographic Attributes of Respondents

Demographic		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Age	21 to 30 years old	26	10.7	10.7	10.7
	31 to 40 years old	109	44.9	44.9	55.6
	41 to 50 years old	83	34.2	34.2	89.7
	Above 50 years old	11	4.5	4.5	94.2
	Below 21 years old	14	5.8	5.8	100.0
	Total	243	100.0	100.0	
Gender	Female	154	63.4	63.4	63.4
	Male	89	36.6	36.6	100.0
	Total	243	100.0	100.0	
Marital Status	Divorced / Widowed	4	1.6	1.6	1.6
	Married	180	74.1	74.1	75.7
	Single	59	24.3	24.3	100.0
	Total	243	100.0	100.0	
Ethnicity	Chinese	208	85.6	85.6	85.6
	Indian	15	6.2	6.2	91.8
	Malay	14	5.8	5.8	97.5
	Others	6	2.5	2.5	100.0
	Total	243	100.0	100.0	
Level of Education	Bachelor Degree	97	39.9	39.9	39.9
	Master Degree	29	11.9	11.9	51.8
	Diploma Level	68	28.0	28.0	79.8
	Certificate	19	7.8	7.8	87.7
	SPM/others	30	12.3	12.3	100.0
	Total	243	100.0	100.0	
Income	< RM 3,000	18	7.4	7.4	7.4
	RM 3,000 to RM 5,000	62	25.5	25.5	32.9
	RM 5,001 to RM 7,000	43	17.7	17.7	50.6
	> RM 7,000	92	37.9	37.9	88.5
	Unemployed	28	11.5	11.5	100.0
	Total	243	100.0	100.0	
Usage of Social	Often	110	45.3	45.3	45.3
	Once a while	26	10.7	10.7	56.0

Media Platforms	Very often	107	44.0	44.0	100.0
	Total	243	100.0	100.0	

The respondent who participated in this study are divided into three main categories. These are customers who purchase or engage with organisation activities very often, often, and once a while. Among the respondents 44% of respondents uses social media 'very often' followed by those who uses 'often' counted 45.3% followed by 'once a while' constitutes 10.7% of respondents. This mean 89.3% of respondents are very frequently uses social media to access to the organisation products or their perception about organisation products or images are influence by the social media marketing activities or information available on social media portrays the image of the organisation among the social media users.

Among the social media users or customers, 63.4% of respondents are female while male constitutes only 36.6% of social media users among the 243 respondents suggesting that women are more engage in social media or online platforms of the organisation. Similarly 79.1% of social media users to access the organizational products or information are from the age group from 30 years to 50 years. Most of the customers who uses social media are married couples who constitutes about 74% of respondents in the sample. Among the social media users in Malaysia, 85% of the sample is Chinese who dominant the social media platforms who engage in organisation. 67.9% of respondents holds a degree or diploma. Those who holds are higher or lower level of academic qualification tends to engage with social media are less compared to those who have bachelor's degree or a diploma. Those who earns above RM7000 tends to engage in social media to access organisational information or involve in purchasing the products from the organisation. This constitutes about 37.9% of the respondents in the sample. Those who earns monthly income between the ranges of RM5001 to RM7000 are about 17.7% which is less than those who earns a lower income between RM3001 to RM5000, who involved in social media platforms constitutes about 25.5%.

3.5. Procedure

The researchers independently contacted the respondents using a non-probability sampling techniques (convenient sampling method) based on time and resource available to reach the target respondents. Samples of 243 respondents were chosen for this study. Additionally, permission from the respondents were obtained before they were approached and send the link through their email. . A time period of 26 days including weekends were spent to collect data. The completed questionnaires were collected by the researchers and a follow up were made by reminding them to through their emails.

3.6. Measures

The social media usage is measured using information search, marketing and branding and customer relations. The mediating variable is customer trust which is measured using five (5) items. Similarly the dependent variable is measured using five (5) items as shown in the table below. The normality, validity and reliability of the measures used in in the items construct was established and illustrated in the table 6 below.

Table 5: Normality Test of Item Scale

Information search	Normality		CFA - Factor Loading	AVE >.50	Reliability >.70
	Skewness	Kurtosis			
I often use social media for general information	-.482	.441	.644	.707	.790
I always use social media to search for products and services	-.803	.732	.802		
I always use social media to search for information about the product suppliers and compare which firm provides best	-.441	-.186	.791		
The company I buy the products or consume the services always use social media to search for customer information	-.202	-.036	.591		
Marketing and Branding					
The company I purchase or consume services always use social media for branding	-.347	.137	.753		

Impact of Social Media Usage on Organisational Image Mediated by Customer Trust

The company I use the product and services always use social media for advertising and promotion of company's products and services	-.435	.306	.792	.766	.849
The company I use the product and services always use social media for conducting marketing research	-.220	.087	.779		
The company I use the product and services always use social media for getting referrals through Word-of-Mouth via likes, shares and comments in Facebook, Twitter and etc.	-.623	.662	.741		
Customer Relations					
The company I use the product and services always use social media to develop customer relations	-.406	.295	.802	.763	.892
The company I use the product and services always use social media to communicate with customers	-.407	.310	.843		
The company I use the product and services always use social media for customer service activities	-.489	.546	.769		
The company I use the product and services always use social media to receive customer feedback on firms existing products and services	-.238	-.164	.762		
The company I use the product and services always use social media to receive customer feedback on new or future products and services	-.502	.011	.726		
The company I use the product and services always use social media to reach new customers	-.326	.299	.678		
Customer Trust					
The social media sites (Facebook, Twitter &etc) of the organisation I used, provides enough safe guards to make me feel comfortable using it to post my information and opinions	-.106	-.348	.777	.811	.905
The social media sites (Facebook, Twitter &etc) of the organisation I used, provides a robust and safe environment in which to transact my information	-.272	-.016	.811		
The organisation I interact to buy the products and services makes me feel assured that legal and technological structures adequately protect me from problems on social media	-.231	-.116	.841		
I really trust the organisation and its social media sites that will not do any harm but protect me from any issues arise	-.163	-.034	.857		
I am very comfortable and relaxed to use the organisation social media sites as I trust the organisation for my past experience with them	-.091	.216	.768		
Organisational Image					
The organisation is a very trust worthy organisation due to its reliable and consistent products and services provided in the past	-.026	.579	.671	.753	.867
The organisation really goes beyond my expectation to build a good relationship with customers	-.158	.307	.659		
The organisation always provides high quality products and services	-.203	.612	.813		
The company name really signifies high quality, reliability and consistency	-.014	-.220	.836		
The company has a good brand name among the people, especially among my friends, colleagues and family	.266	-.367	.784		

In this study, the normality is tested by using combines the tests of skewness and kurtosis, and the statistical significance of skewness and kurtosis are two key indicators to measure the data normality (Liang, Tang & Zhao, 2019).Hair et al. (2012) argued that data is considered to be normal if skewness is between - 2 to +2 and kurtosis is between - 7 to +7.Based on 243 responses, the normality test of this study returned an average of skewness range from -0.836 to 0.266 and a kurtosis values range from -0.367 to 0.732 suggesting that the data collected are normally distributed as the Skewness and Kurtosis values are in the acceptable range (Hair, et al., 2012). Therefore the distribution

considered symmetrical. The positive outcome of the normality testing therefore, confirms the dataset for further research.

To test the validity, first, the exploratory factor analysis was carried out. From this study, the loading on each factor is sufficient as the values range between 0.474 to 0.725. Since all the values are above 0.4 suggested that the items in the construct are valid. The CFA was performed to establish the convergent validity through factor loading and through average variance extracted (AVE). Factor loading and AVE is used to assess the construct convergent validity of a measurement procedure (Basit, Tiong & Hassan, 2020). The loading of each item on each construct must exceed more than 0.4 (Basit et al, 2020). As all the items in the construct have a loading above 0.644, it is considered that the construct is valid for further analysis (SEM). Also Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is above 0.5 suggested that the construct is convergent valid (Radhakrishnan, Basit & Hassan, 2018). Similarly, discriminant validity applies to identified the same indicators should explain a much lower proportion of variance from other latent variables (Basit, Wong, Hassan & Sethumadhavan, 2020). Discriminant validity is important to measure the validity construct in this research. As proposed by Evans (1996), correlation is an effect size and can be describe the strength where the absolute value should be less than 0.80. Likewise, Hair et al. (2011) and Hair et al. (2012) suggested the acceptable squared correlations value is less than 1.00. Table 6 below show the correlation between the all combination of constructs stay below 0.800 with perceive ease of use and e-business successful implementation have the lowest value of 0.595. Likewise, in squared correlations, the collected data shows all have the value are lower than the threshold and the highest value achieved is 0.543 and both results concluded the construct is valid and acceptable. Also the squared correlations are lower than the AVE values suggesting that there is sufficient discriminant validity (Hair et al, 2011, Radhakrishnan et al, 2018).

Table 6: Discriminant Validity

	Information Search	Marketing and Branding	Customer Relations	Trust	Organisational Image
Information Search	1.000	0.620	0.625	0.404	0.394
Marketing and Branding	0.384	1.000	0.834	0.353	0.465
Customer Relations	0.391	0.696	1.000	0.409	0.478
Trust	0.163	0.125	0.167	1.000	0.603
Organisational Image	0.155	0.216	0.229	0.364	1.000
AVE	0.707	0.766	0.763	0.811	0.753
The squared correlations are below the diagonal are and squared correlations values					

To further test the validity of the construct, the construct reliability test was carried out and the result are illustrated in the table 5 above. The Cronbach’s values are above 0.7 suggested that the items in the construct are highly reliable (Hair et al, 2011). With reference to Hair et al (2011), it is indicated that there is a high internal consistency among the items in the construct as the Cronbach Alpha values are above 0.7 suggesting high reliability. A good reliability criterion is with estimate at 0.7 or higher, which means that all observed variables consistently represent the same latent construct (Hair et al., 2011). Table 5 above shows the calculated composite reliability of this research for each latent construct, and all result show 0.70 and above which means the model is good fit. It is important to evaluate the reliability of supplied data in a research study to ensure the excellent test quality is achieved (Basit et al, 2020). Item interrelatedness and dimensionality may affect the value of alpha, and the acceptable range of Cronbach's alpha for a reliability construct is ranging from 0.70 to 0.95 (Hair et al, 2013). Table above show all four independent and one dependent variables are within the acceptable range and above the value of 0.95, which show the data is high reliability.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.2. Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is a statistical technique used when investigating the structure of multivariate data and test whether a hypothesized structure is appropriate for multivariate data (Fox, 2010). The four-major purpose of the CFA are (1) psychometric evaluation of measures; (2) construct validation; (3) testing method effect; and (4) testing measurement invariance (Brown, 2006). This study used CFA to examine the research's proposed model either it

fits with the factor loadings and other indices such as chi-square test, root mean square error of approximation and comparative fit index via statistical package ~ AMOS 22. According to Holmes-Smith et al. (2006), there are several fitness indexes in Confirmatory factor analysis that affected the fitness of the model to the data and suggested to use of at least on fitness index from each category of model fit.

Figure 2: Measurement of Latent Variables
Source: AMOS outputs

Chi Square is a test which makes a statement about the nature of the distribution for the whole population (Moore, 2017). The P-values, as the smallest level of significance, was recorded as 0.00 in which the validity of the research data is confirmed. According to Lai (2019) Comparative Fit Index (CFI) defined as the discrepancy function adjusted for sample size which the larger value indicating better fit and a good model CFI should exceed 0.90. This research was considered to be a good fit model with the CFI result of 0.910. It was suggested by Schubert, Hagemann, Voss & Bergmann (2017) that Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) values less than 0.05 are good, value between 0.05 and 0.08 are moderate, values between 0.08 to 0.10 are marginal and value greater than 0.1 consider unacceptable, meanwhile according to Basit et al (2020), the RMSEA between 0.08 to 0.10 show the model is mediocre fit, hence, the model of this research is consider as acceptable model fit with RMSEA of 0.088. This is also a more parsimonious research which should have normed chi-squares index lesser than 5. This research have normed chi-square value of 2.032 (Basit et al, 2020). Overall the model fitness is achieved as illustrated in the table 7 below.

Table 7: Model Fitness Indexes

Name of Category	Name of Index	Level of Acceptance	CFA Result
Absolute Fit	Chisq	P > 0.05	0.0001
	RMSEA	< 0.10	0.073
	Normed Chi-Square	<3.0	2.276
Incremental Fit	CFI	> 0.90	0.910
Parsimonious Fit	Chisq/DF	< 5.0	2.276

4.3. Structural Equation Modelling

The causal structure model as per figure 3 was formulated to test the hypothesis of social media usage (information search, marketing and branding, customer relations) and trust on organizational image as well as mediating role of trust. The validity of the structural model can be examined in various ways, which first through the indices such as normed chi-square, chi-square, CFI and RMSEA (Hair, et al., 2011). Following this, figure 3 indicates a chi-square is significant with $p=0.000$ (chi-square is 550.720, $df=242$). The CFI scored 0.910 which is higher than the threshold value of 0.9 (Hair, et al., 2011), which suggest the model as a good fit. The RMSEA is 0.073 which is less than 0.08 which considers it's perfectly a goof fit model (Hair et al, 2011). The normed chi-square is less than 3 (in this case 2.276). Also the values of the CFA model fitness indices and SEM model fit indices are closely matched, suggested that this SEM is valid.

Figure 3: SEM-Social Media usage effect on Organisational Image through Customer Trust
Source: AMOS outputs

The above model suggests that social media usage dimensions such as information search, customer relations and marketing and branding do not have any significant impact on brand image as the significant values are more than 0.05. However the trust has a positive and significant impact on organizational image with estimate value of 0.485 ($p=0.0001$) suggesting that when customer perceived level of trust goes up, it improves organizational image. Also Information search has a positive and significant image on level of trust with an estimate coefficient value of 0.250 ($P=0.013$) which is below 0.05 indicating that social media enabled information search would increase level of trust on organization resulting improved organizational image.

To further analyse and establish the mediating effect of customer trust on the relationship between social media usage and organizational image, the path analysis was re-run with the level of customer trust as a latent variable (independent variable along with social media usage variables). The below figure 4 suggests that social media usage dimensions such as information search, customer relations and marketing and branding do not have any significant impact on brand image as the significant values are more than 0.05. However the trust has a positive and significant impact on organizational image with estimate value of 0.485 ($p=0.0001$) suggesting that when customer perceived level of trust goes up, it improves organizational image.

Figure 4: SEM-Direct effect of Social Media usage and customer trust on Organisational Image
 Source: AMOS outputs

The table below shows that all the SEM models meets the model fit indices except fit indices and models are valid to proceed with SEM to examine the causal impact of the social media usage on organizational image mediated by the customer trust. Also as the values are same, it shows that the construct and the model is convergent valid (Hair et al, 2011). The table 8 shows that all the SEM models meets the model fit indices except fit indices and models are valid to proceed with SEM to examine the causal impact of the social media usage on organizational image mediated by the customer trust. Also as the values are same, it shows that the construct and the model is convergent valid (Hair et al, 2011).

Table 8: Model fitness Comparison

Mode fitness	Chi-square	P value	CFI	Normed Chi-square	RMSEA
CFA	550.720	0.000	0.910	2.276	0.073
SEM1	550.720	0.000	0.910	2.276	0.073
SEM2	550.720	0.000	0.910	2.276	0.073

Based on the below table 9, it was clear that social media has no significant impact on organizational image. It was found only information search has a positive and significant impact on level of trust and trust has a significant impact on organizational image. Although there is no evidence indicating that social media has any significant impact on organizational image directly or indirectly. However, level of trust has positive and significant impact on organizational image. It is worth to note that the level of trust has no mediating impact on the relationship between social media usage and organizational image as the estimate coefficient do not change at all in either case where trust is analyses as complete mediator or trust is analyses along with social media usage dimensions linking with organizational image.

Table 9: Model –Analysis of Social Media usage and Mediating effect of Trust on Organisational Image

Model -Impact of Social Media Usage on Organisational Image mediate by Customer Trust							
	Hypotheses		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Accepted/ Rejected
Trust	<---	Information Search (IS)	.250	.162	2.491	.013	Rejected
Trust	<---	Marketing and Branding(MB)	-.042	.176	-.269	.788	Rejected
Trust	<---	Customer Relation (CR)	.288	.204	1.871	.061	Rejected
O.Image	<---	Customer Trust (Trust)	.485	.053	6.155	.001	Accepted
O.Image	<---	Marketing and Branding (MB)	.196	.106	1.404	.160	Rejected
O.Image	<---	Customer Relations (CR)	.112	.122	.817	.414	Rejected
O.Image	<---	Information search (IS)	.007	.095	.078	.937	Rejected
Model : Impact of Social Media Usage and Customer Trust on Organisational Image							
	Hypotheses		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Accepted/ Rejected
O.Image	<---	Customer Trust (Trust)	.485	.053	6.155	.0001	Accepted
O.Image	<---	Marketing and Branding (MB)	.196	.106	1.404	.160	Rejected
O.Image	<---	Customer Relations (CR)	.112	.122	.817	.414	Rejected
O.Image	<---	Information search (IS)	.007	.095	.078	.937	Rejected

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

There are four key objectives that this study investigated by collecting and analyzing data. These objectives are to examine the impact of social media on organizational image and trust, and trust on organizational image and finally testing the mediating role of trust. It was found that social media dimensions such as information search, marketing and branding and customer relations do not have any direct or indirect influence on organizational image. This very contrary to previous research such as Etter et al (2019), Kim et al (2017), Vistbacka (2017), Singh et al (2020), Amegbe, et al(2017), Bilgin, 2018). However Bilgin (2018) result was in alignment of our findings as he found a weak influence of social media usage on brand image through brand awareness. Previous studies done in Malaysia as well contradicts with our findings with past research done by Hanaysha (2016) and a study conducted in Malaysia in automobile brand with notable presence by Adetunji et al (2018). Wijesundara, et al., (2017) found that social media can be a great tool to influence customer by enhancing organisational image through the two-way communications. However, Jokinen (2016) founds that social media usage show important associations with customer’s understanding of the effect of social media on brand image.

We also found no significant impact of marketing and branding on organizational image and customer trust. Also we found no significant impact of customer relations on organizational image and customer trust. Our finding contradicts with most of the past research findings. In the past, it was found that social media influences customer trust (Singhal, 2016; Hariyana, & Berililana, 2017; Choi & Lee, 2017; Liu et al, 2018; Esenyel & Girgen, 2019; Tümer et al, 2019; Manzoor et al, 2020; Manzoor et al, 2020). Despite our finding is not in alignment with the past literature, more recently also it was found that personality and information disclosure from social media usage had a positive and significant effect on e-word-of-mouth and e-word-of-mouth has a significant and positive impact on customer trust (Seo, Park & Choi, 2020).

This study well establish the fact that trust has a significant and positive impact on organizational image. This is similar to previous studies such as Seo et al (2020) found that customer trust has a positive and significant effect on brand awareness and brand image. Also Deheshti et al (2016) found that customer trust increases, the organisational image in terms of brand image and perception of organisation in the eyes of customer improved. Also in the past it was argued that customer trust depends how customer perceive the level of service quality, product reliability and information available for customers, which forms the impression and image of the organisation (Liat et al, 2017). Also additional evidence suggested that when customer's perceived level of trust increases towards organisational products, brand image and overall service delivery results positive organisational image (Song, Wang & Han, 2019). In aligned with our findings, it was found that the customer trust level increase when organisation starts to fulfill the promises made to customer (Agag& El-Masry, 2017). As result reliability and dependability of the organisation improves leading to positive organisational image (Hwang & Choi, 2019; Yilmaz & Ari, 2017). However this study failed in establishing the fact that trust has a mediating impact on social media usage and organizational image. Our finding again contradicts with Mabkhot et al, (2017); AdebisinandMwalugha (2020) where they found that customer trust plays an important role in mediating the relationship between social media usage and marketing activities.

Therefore we concluded that the level of customer trust must be enhanced and cultivated through effective use of social media usage. This means when the level of customer trust increases with the products or organizational brand, which will in turn would improve organizational image. This means organization must emphasis on allocating more resources to enhance level of customer trust associated with the organization products and brand.

VI. IMPLICATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTION

This study have established the social media usage and customer trust as two key determinants of organizational image, which is considered as new contributions to the theories of social media and organizational and marketing theories. This study also identified the mediating effects of customer trust on the relationship of social media usage elements such as information search, marketing & branding and customer relations with organizational image. Results from this study would enables SME companies to make policy decisions on enhancing managers' customer trust to improve and enhance organizational image. This study will contribute by identifying the lacking dimensions of social media usage, which are crucial for enhancing their organizational image such as information search, marketing & branding and customer relations. This study enabled to establish that fact that level of customer trust is more important to create through various social media activities to enhance the organizational image.

The result of this research made the contributions to the theoretical domains of Technology Adoption Models (TAM), Planned Behavior Theories (PBT), and Innovation Diffusion Theory (IDT), Theories of Organisational Image and Relationship Marketing Theories. This study confirms that social media usage and customer trust are two key components to determine the organizational image. Especially the customer trust is an important component in determining the organization image. This means customer trust can be used to enhance the key elements of planned behavior and technology adoption model either as part of the theory or a moderating variable in adopting social media to enhance organizational image. In terms of practical implication, this study contributes in developing policies and strategies to develop and enhance customer trust to improve organizational image. This means marketing managers must intervene to provide training to enhance customer relationship and trust. Organizations must formulate policies to govern the use of social media and its related information to ensure social media platforms are used carefully and to benefit the organization rather than using it for personal use. Identifying appropriate methods to deployed the social media uses such as information search, marketing and branding and customer relations must be carefully design and monitored to enhance organizational image.

Therefore, this study developed the measures for social media usage construct based on various purposes for which it can be used. It categorized the usage construct into three sub constructs and measured various purposes of usage, such as social media use for information search, social media use for marketing, and social media use for customer service. Thus, this study contributed to the enhancement of the measurement of usage construct especially in social media context. Furthermore the study also clearly identifies and categorizes the impact of social media usage on organizations in terms of various sub-constructs such as cost reduction in marketing and customer service, enhanced customer relations, and improved information accessibility. Therefore, future researchers can investigate the impact of social media usage based on the categorization of the impact factors identified in this study and prove the results in different contexts.

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